

DELIVERABLE D2.3 V3

REPORT DESCRIBING THE CROSS-OMICS DEMONSTRATORS

Demonstrate added value of the cross-omics analysis to Personalised Medicine in disease demonstrator

WP2 – Data Stewardship and integration of omic research in Personalised Medicine

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

We investigated to what extent metabolomic analysis would add to a genetic analysis of a complex rare genetic-metabolic disease. We analysed a cohort of 150 pediatric patients ¹suffering from neurodevelopmental disorders, together with their parents, for genetic variants using whole genome and exome sequencing. Part of this cohort (40 patients) was suitable and was investigated for metabolic changes of a comprehensive targeted metabolite biomarker panel using mass spectrometry. We applied tools of the Multi-Omics Toolbox for data quality control and statistical analyses, to assess the utility and applicability of these tools in an independent cross-omics study.

The study yielded a positive diagnosis of 30% of the 150 patients based on genetic analyses. The untargeted metabolomics data showed batch effects among the different runs which could successfully be corrected using the batch correction approaches from the EATRIS-Plus Multi-Omics Toolbox. Subsequent targeted metabolomic data analysis did not add functional diagnosis using the panel of 350 preselected and annotated metabolic biomarkers. We did observe differential metabolites which were seen in our diagnostic screening before but which are annotated as food-related and not relevant for diagnosis. The untargeted metabolomic data was made ready for extensive data analysis, which was beyond the scope of the current study.

PROJECT OBJECTIVES

Our flagship project EATRIS-Plus aims to build further capabilities and deliver innovative scientific tools to support the long-term sustainability strategy of EATRIS as one of Europe's key European research infrastructures for Personalised Medicine.

The main goals of the EATRIS-Plus will be to:

- Consolidate EATRIS capacities in the field of Personalised Medicine (particularly omics technologies) to better serve academia and industry and augment the number of EATRIS Innovation Hubs with large pharma;
- Drive patient empowerment through active involvement in the infrastructure's operations;
- Expand strategic partnerships with research infrastructures and other relevant stakeholders, and
- Further strengthen the long-term sustainability of the EATRIS financial model.
- Develop a Multi-omic Toolbox for researchers.

DETAILED REPORT ON THE DELIVERABLE

BACKGROUND

Genetic analysis has strongly increased the diagnostic yield in rare diseases. In clinical diagnostics, many institutes are now following a 'DNA first' approach, supported by the comprehensive public libraries of genetic-disease relationships, that are rapidly increasing in content.

¹ Board-certified clinical geneticists counseled all 150 patients and their parents for the ES-based SOC/GS procedures. All participants or their legal representatives gave written informed consent. This study was approved by the Medical Review Ethics Committee Arnhem-Nijmegen under 2011/188 and 2020-7142.

Multi-omics analyses have the potential to add insight in mechanisms of disease by enriching diagnostic datasets. However, whereas whole exome and genome sequencing analysis yields many diagnostic variants that are statistically strongly related to the phenotype, many variants still have an unknown functional significance. A large challenge for progressing these variants in personalised diagnosis is our current inability to reliably predict or even measure their functional impact in individual patients. Consequently, genetic analysis is in many cases based on statistical correlations without functional annotation. A second challenge is to diagnose the remaining fraction of cases that do not display a convincingly diagnostic genetic variant, and to start understanding the differential disease response in patients with same genetic disease.

Whereas genetic analysis predicts a high/low risk for rare genetic-metabolic diseases, more functional omics platforms such as transcriptomic, proteomic, lipidomic and metabolomic analyses have the potential to complement this in multi-omics fashion and provide the functional answers to the two challenges stated above. Of these, metabolomic analyses are strongly complementary as metabolomic (biochemical) analytes have already been measured using standardised clinical chemistry tests and much knowledge on biomarker-disease correlation has been acquired in the past 100 years.

Here, we investigated, as cross-omic demonstrator, to what extent metabolomic analysis would add to a genetic analysis of a complex rare genetic-metabolic disease. We selected a cohort of 150 pediatric patients suffering from neurodevelopmental disorders, and analysed these together with their parents for genetic variants. Part of this cohort was suitable for metabolic analysis which was investigated as a comprehensive targeted metabolite biomarker panel using mass spectrometry. We applied tools of the Multi-Omics Toolbox for data Quality Control and statistical analyses, to assess the utility and applicability of these tools in an independent cross-omics study.

DESCRIPTION OF WORK

We aimed to demonstrate the added value of developing cross-omic analysis by using multi-omics data sets to understand the mechanism of disease, expanding on genomic analyses and with the aim of contextualising identified genetic variations. As a demonstrator, we focused on a cohort of 150 patients with neurodevelopment disorders that were thoroughly investigated using genetic and metabolomics analysis in a standardised clinical diagnostic setting.

We performed both full genome (GS) and exome (ES) sequencing in 150 consecutive NDD patient-parent trios. The primary outcome was diagnostic yield, calculated from disease-causing variants affecting exonic sequence of known NDD genes. GS (30%, $n = 45$) and ES (29%, $n = 43$) had similar diagnostic yield. All 43 conclusive diagnoses obtained with ES testing were also identified by GS. ES, however, required integration of multiple test results to obtain these diagnoses. GS yielded two more conclusive diagnoses, and four more possible diagnoses than ES (35 vs. 31). Interestingly, these six variants detected only by GS were copy number variants. This work was published in 2022 in *Eur. J. Hum. Gen.* (2023), doi 10.1038/s41431-022-01185-9).

As neurodevelopmental disorders can have a functional metabolic impairment too, we aimed to analyse these 150 trio's by metabolomic as well. Such metabolomic data could potentially provide functional annotation data for the genetic variants with unknown functional significance (challenge 1 stated above), or could provide additional diagnosis (challenge 2 stated above). For this, we required

heparin plasma from the trio subjects (parents and patient) which could be obtained for only part of the cohort. After stringent quality assessment of the plasma samples, we selected 40 patient-parent trios for metabolomic analysis. We applied the Next Generation Metabolic Sequencing (NGMS) panel of 350 metabolic biomarkers, that are linked to over 100 inherited metabolic disorders (see Coene et al, *J Inherit Metab Dis* (2018), doi 10.1007/s10545-017-0131-6; and Hoegen et al, *Metabolites* (2021), doi 10.3390/metabo11090568). In this method, which is being applied in routine clinical diagnostics in our laboratory at RUMC, metabolomic data is acquired in an untargeted manner after which the preselected panel of m/z features corresponding to 350 metabolites is extracted from the data and interrogated statistically and biologically, and applying the knowledge base our diagnostic metabolic laboratory over the past decades.

The 40 patient samples were analysed in 4 batches, screened by positive and negative ionisation mode in duplicate. After removal of a clear outlier (duplicate sample of one father sample), we noted batch differences (Fig 1 A). Batch correction was done by applying the 5 different methods as developed in the EATRIS-Plus WP2 data analysis team, being: Limma, QC_rlsc, QC_RSC, ComBAT and BatchCorr. Of these, ComBAT performed the best (Fig 1B for representative graph).

Figure 1 Batch correction of untargeted metabolomics data. Principal Component Analysis plots indicating four batches (indicated by colour), each of which contained Patient, QC and validation samples (indicated by symbol). A. Before batch correction all samples of one batch cluster together. B. After ComBAT non-parametric correction patient, QC and validation samples cluster together as is desired.

The 40 patient samples were subsequently analysed using NGMS, quantitating 350 functionally relevant metabolic biomarkers. No differential behaviour of these metabolic biomarkers was found beyond predefined statistical thresholds of clinical significance.

One differential metabolite was noted (Figure 2), that was observed independently before in a patient suffering from the inherited disorder NANS. The compound was not part of the panel of 350 metabolites, and was putatively annotated as Vanillic acid. Its identify was confirmed by repeat analysis with a purified standard. Investigation of Vanillic acid in the Human Metabolome Database (HMDB0000484) indicated a food-related origin with no reported biological function in metabolic pathways.

Figure 2 Differential behaviour of a specific metabolite in the NGMS analysis. Indicated is a box plot of the relative intensity of a metabolite with feature mass 168.03835, RT 6,28 and isotope C13 in duplicate measurements of multiple patients with neurodevelopmental disorders (indicated in grey), validation samples (green) and QC samples (blue). Patient samples where this metabolite was strongly increased is indicated in red. The metabolite was later identified as Vanillic acid (HMDB0000484).

NEXT STEPS

The batch-corrected untargeted metabolomic dataset of patients and parents was made ready for subsequent multi-variate data analysis, in which inter-individual metabolomic differences can be revealed and annotated to food, medication or endogenous metabolic pathways. This, however, is beyond the scope of the deliverable D2.3 of the EATRIS-Plus project, and which will be followed by scientists of the Netherlands X-omics Initiative.

The obtained metabolic data will be submitted to public MetaboLights data repository at the European Bioinformatics Institute (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/metabolights/>) using the workflow as described in the EATRIS-Plus data management plan, thus complying with the defined FAIR data principles.

ABBREVIATIONS

GS	Genome sequencing
ES	Exome sequencing
MS	Mass spectrometry
QC	Quality control
NGMS	Next Generation Metabolic Screening
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable

DELIVERY AND SCHEDULE

Extension requested on 22/11 (approved 24/11) until 30/06/23. Version 2 submitted 22/12/2023

ADJUSTMENTS MADE

The deliverable was suggested to be updated by the project's ethics committee on the premise that informed consent information was not described for the 150 paediatric cohort. It is now added as footnote 1.

APPENDICES

Batch correction results

Batch correction results

ID Trios project

Batch information

ESI_Pos	ESI_Neg
191104	191119
191112	191121
200128	200131
191004	191015

Batch correction methods

Method name	Short Description	Reference
Limma (removeBatchEffect)	General model	Ritchie et al., 2015
QC_rlsc	Uses technical replicates	Derks, 2016
QC-RSC	Uses technical replicates	Jankevics and Weber, 2021
ComBAT (parametric and non-parametric)	General model	Leek et al., 2012
BatchCorr	Uses technical replicates	Brunius et al., 2016

Merged batches without correction: POS mode

Outliers:

QT_200128_36, QT_200128_99: replicates corresponding to Patient plasma BB19-00863, which is the father in the Trios set 038

Merged batches without correction: NEG mode

Outliers:

QT_200131_36, QT_200131_99: replicates corresponding to Patient plasma BB19-00863, which is the father in the Trios set 038

Batch correction all samples: POS mode

Note: Outliers removed

Batch correction QC's: POS mode

Batch correction all samples: NEG mode

Note: Outliers removed

Batch correction QC's: NEG mode

